

Observation of reversible light degradation in organic photovoltaics induced by long-persistent radicals

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Abstract

With the rapid development of organic photovoltaics, device stability has become a crucial obstacle hindering their transition from laboratory to industrial applications. However, it remains still unclear how light differs from heat in driving trap formation and leads to device degradation. On the basis of the PTzBI-dF:Y6-BO system, it is observed that the post-thermal annealing on these high-performance organic solar cells can partially recover the light-induced burn-in losses. The recovery process is found to be correlated with a reversible charge extraction ability, reversible trap density of state, local charge carrier density and charge accumulation. We propose in this work an innovative mechanism for light degradation in organic photovoltaic devices, which is triggered by the presence of light-induced long-persistent radicals. The findings offer deep insights into light degradation of organic photovoltaics and a new perspective for improving device stability under long-term operation.

Broader context

The longevity of organic photovoltaic (OPV) devices, consisting of burn-in loss and long-term stability, is highly correlated with the nature of employed materials and external factors. Previous studies have reported the existence of long-persistent radicals in organic photoactive materials. However, there is a lack of systematic investigation regarding the impact of these radicals on OPV device performance and operational stability. In this work, a correlation between the presence of long-persistent radicals in the non-fullerene photovoltaic material systems and the light-induced burn-in loss is established. Accordingly, we propose a novel light degradation mechanism that is related to the existence of long-persistent radicals in the blend film, which is distinct from the degradation mechanisms induced by morphological evolution and chemical degradation.

1. Introduction

The operational stability of organic photovoltaics (OPVs), which is one of the most crucial challenges during the transition from laboratory-scale to industrial applications, relies primarily on material systems¹⁻⁴. A typical ageing process mainly consists of burn-in loss and long-term degradation. Previous studies have reported the correlation of long-term degradation with encapsulation or chemical stability⁵, while burn-in loss can result from injection or extraction problems caused by chemical degradation, interface defects, and bulk morphological evolution. Chemical degradation, including crosslinking reaction among polymer donors^{6,7}, dimerization of fullerene acceptors⁸, oxidation reaction^{9,10}, degradation of the terminal group of non-fullerene acceptors (NFAs)¹¹, and chemical reaction of interface layers^{12,13} as well as electrode failure^{14,15}, can be triggered by heat, oxygen doping or ultraviolet (UV) exposure.

Morphology evolution, including demixing of fullerenes^{16,17}, diffusion-limited secondary aggregation of NFAs^{18,19} and rearrangement of molecular orientation^{20,21}, is mainly caused by the accumulation of heat and incompatibility of donors and acceptors²². In fullerene-based systems, the chemical degradation and demixing of donor and acceptor caused by incompatibility led to drop in fill factor (FF) and short-circuit current density (J_{SC}). In NFA-based systems, the observed burn-in loss stemmed primarily from the reduction of electron mobilities and consequently compromising FF.^{20,23} Degradation in open-circuit voltage (V_{OC}) can be observed when higher energetic disorder led to broader density of state (DOS) or when charge recombination process became more pronounced, resulting in a lower charge carrier density or higher non-radiative energy loss.²⁴ Despite the achievement of devices with improved stability through molecular design^{25,26}, morphology adjustment²⁷⁻³¹ and interface engineering^{32,33}, the specific roles played by light and heat in the

degradation process of organic solar cells (OSCs), especially in high-performance NFAs-based systems, remains still unclear. In general, light can be converted to heat through non-radiative recombination process, and the heat accumulation can act as a driving force for molecular motion, which facilitates the transition of metastable blend morphology to a stable state. In reality, the evolution of those processes is more complex, because light could drive photoactive materials to high-energy excited states. The precise calculation or measurement of the processes occurring in such states remains a challenge at present.

In this study, we demonstrate the observation of a reversible light ageing process for high-performance NFA-based OSCs, and determine the causes of light-induced burn-in loss. PTzBI-dF and Y6-BO are used as the model system, which exhibits excellent long-term stability but pronounced burn-in loss under light ageing. Evidence indicates that post-thermal annealing (TA) process can reverse the degradation of OSCs, in terms of J_{SC} and FF. Additionally, light intensity and transient measurements suggest that this reversible effect on J_{SC} and FF is accompanied by reversible field-dependent charge extraction. However, the whole V_{OC} loss is irreversible due to increased charge carrier recombination, decreased charge carrier lifetime, and broader DOS.

More interestingly, long-persistent charge carriers in disorder solid with lifetime over one month were also observed in previous studies.³⁴ To address those findings of light-induced degradation in high-performance NFA systems, we propose a novel explanation that the reversible light ageing process can be attributed to the presence of light-induced long-persistent radicals. Light soaking and the resulting high local charge carrier density facilitate the formation of long-persistent radicals, and TA treatment can provide activation energy to the complete or partial release of captured charges, thereby restoring device performance.

2. Results

2.1. Reversible stability via post-thermal annealing

The OPV material system, PTzBI-dF:Y6-BO, can be processed with a halogen-free solvent *o*-xylene, achieving an impressively high power conversion efficiency (PCE) of over 17% (Fig. S1, ESI†).²⁷ For stability study, we fabricated OSCs with an inverted device structure of ITO/ZnO NPs/PTzBI-dF:Y6-BO/MoO_x/Ag. The active layers of PTzBI-dF:Y6-BO were thermally annealed at 110 °C for 10 min before evaporation for optimized device fabrication. The ageing process was conducted under continuous 1 sun equivalent illumination provided by white LED (400–700 nm). The temperature of samples was controlled in the range of 40–45 °C. As shown in Fig. 1a and b, the control device based on PTzBI-dF:Y6-BO exhibited excellent long-term stability, suggesting the stable chemical structures of both donor and acceptor materials. However, pronounced burn-in losses, particularly in J_{sc} and FF, were observed in the first 100 hours. An FF burn-in loss in NFA systems can be commonly explained by the secondary crystallization of NFAs, molecular reorientation, and the decline in electron mobility.^{20,35} Interestingly, we discovered that the degradation in J_{sc} and FF of PTzBI-dF:Y6-BO under illumination can be recovered by subjecting the aged devices to a TA treatment at 110°C/ 10 min (Fig. 1c-e). The reversible degradation phenomena were also observed consistently in other different material systems (Fig. S2, ESI†). The thermal-driven recovery process suggests that the burn-in loss in this case may not stem from permanent chemical bond breaking or heat accumulation. Instead, it is likely attributed to reversible factors induced by light stress.

Fig. 1 The evolution of device stability under 1 sun illumination under an open-circuit mode: (a) $J-V$ curves of control devices normalized to initial J_{SC} value. (b) Normalized device parameters of control devices. (c) $J-V$ curves of TA-treated aged devices normalized to initial J_{SC} value. (d) Normalized J_{SC} degradation for TA-treated aged devices. (e) Normalized device parameters for TA-treated aged devices. Yellow dashed lines represent in-situ TA treatments at 110 °C for 10 min in nitrogen.

2.2. Morphology evolution, recombination dynamics and mobilities

To identify the factors influencing reversible light-induced degradation, we conducted systematic characterizations from various aspects, including light harvesting, morphology evolution, exciton dissociation and charge transport. In-situ UV-vis absorption spectra in Fig. 2a show no visible change in both peak position and strength, excluding chemical degradation in active layer as the cause for a decrease in light harvesting. The grazing-incidence wide-angle X-ray scattering (GIWAXS) measurements, as shown in Fig. 2b-d and Fig. S3 (ESI[†]), reveal that the ordered phases of PTzBI-dF:Y6-BO remained nearly unchanged. External quantum efficiency (EQE) spectra show an overall decrease over 10% in response intensity across the entire absorption wavelength range, indicating that the degradation in J_{SC} was not caused by donor or acceptor individually. The application of bias during

the EQE measurement facilitated the extraction of the maximum photogenerated charge carriers (Fig. S4e, ESI†), and the maximum photogenerated charge carriers showed negligible change at bias of -2 V. Similar results can be obtained from charge extraction probability $P(E, T)$ versus effective voltage (V_{eff}) measurements (Fig. 2f and Fig. S4a, ESI†), suggesting that the aged devices experience difficulties in field-dependence charge extraction. Nevertheless, this problem could be mitigated by thermal annealing.

The exponential factor α extracted from the J_{SC} dependence on light-intensity (P_{light}) measurements indicates that bimolecular recombination was weak in all devices (Fig. 2g). After light ageing, the slope of the $V_{\text{OC}}-P_{\text{light}}$ plot increased from $1.13 kT/q$ to $1.42kT/q$, and then decreased to $1.32kT/q$ after TA treatment. This observation suggests that the increased trap-assist recombination induced by light ageing process can be mitigated by TA treatment (Fig. 2h). Furthermore, the $\text{FF}-P_{\text{light}}$ dependence plot also demonstrated a distinct trend after subjecting the aged devices to the TA process or UV light exposure for 1 min (Figs. 2i and S4b-c, ESI†), further confirming the effectiveness of the reversible process. Fig. 2j displays the charge carrier lifetime as a function of voltage determined through transient photovoltage (TPV) measurement. After the light ageing process, the charge carrier lifetime decreased by less than one order of magnitude and remained nearly unchanged after the TA process. The dependence of charge carrier density on voltage was determined through transient charge extraction (CE) measurements (Fig. 2k). After ageing process, the charge carrier density increased under the same voltage, representing an increase in DOS. However, the charge carrier density was close to $1.08 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ under the corresponding V_{OC} of devices in different states (fresh, 0.85 V; ageing, 0.82 V; and TA, 0.81 V). A broader DOS after light ageing with no change in charge carrier density resulted in an irreversible V_{OC} loss during the burn-in process.²⁴

Fig. 2 (a) In-situ UV-vis absorption spectra of active layer spin-coated on glass. GIWAXS measurement for (b) fresh, (c) aged and (d) TA-treated film. (e) EQE spectra. (f) Charge dissociation probability $P(E, T)$ versus V_{eff} . Light intensity dependence measurements for (g) J_{sc} , (h) V_{oc} and (i) FF. (j) Charge carrier lifetime as a function of V_{oc} detected by TPV. (k) Charge carrier density as a function of V_{oc} detected by CE; arrows and dashed lines represent V_{oc} under 1 sun illumination. (l) Hole and electron mobility measured by SCLC method via hole-only and electron-only devices, in comparison with dynamic device mobility measured by photo-CELIV via OSCs.

Previous studies reported that degradation in mobility caused by heat or light ageing, particularly in electron mobility, is one of the most crucial factors contributing to the increased recombination and overall device degradation in NFA-based OSCs.^{20,23} Herein, the space-charge-limited current (SCLC) method was used to calculate the electron mobilities and hole mobilities based on electron-only devices (ITO/ZnO/active layer/PFN-Br/Ag) and hole-only devices (ITO/2PACz/active layer/MoO_x/Ag) (Fig. S5 and S6, ESI[†]). Interestingly, the results shown in Fig. 2l and Table S1 (ESI[†]) exhibit only minor changes in both electron and hole mobility. In contrast, the photoinduced charge carriers extracted by linearly increasing voltage (photo-CELIV) method,³⁶ which provide insight into the dynamic device

mobility within OSCs, demonstrated contrasting results (Fig. 21 and Fig. S7, ESI†). The dynamic device mobility decreased from $1.37 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ in fresh devices, to $8.29 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ in aged devices, and subsequently partially recovered back to $1.26 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ in TA-treated aged devices. The results obtained from SCLC method demonstrate no obvious change in charge transporting channels within the active layers, corroborating the findings of the morphology analysis (Fig. 2b-d), while the results from photo-CELIV provide compelling evidence that light ageing process could hinder charge extraction in operational OSCs. Furthermore, the effect of active layer thicknesses (90 and 130 nm) on the reversible process was also investigated (Fig. S8, ESI†). Devices combined with thicker active layers exhibited a more pronounced burn-in loss and a larger recovery amplitude after TA, because the thicker-film devices with weakened electric field suffer from a more pronounced extraction problem during the ageing process.

2.3. Drift-diffusion simulation

Fig. 3 Drift-diffusion simulations of devices parameters as a function of (a) electron mobility, (b) bimolecular recombination efficiency and (c) electron trap density.

To identify factors that contributed to the reversible degradation in J_{sc} and FF, we reconstructed the $J-V$ curve based on a drift-diffusion model by using the commercial optoelectronic simulation

software SETFOS. Oxygen or water doping in active layer and interfaces is usually accompanied by degradation in V_{OC} and FF,³⁷⁻⁴⁰ but the reversible trend in V_{OC} was not observed in the degradation process, the impact of those factors was excluded from the simulation. Accordingly, we mimicked the impact of the changes in charge carrier mobility, bimolecular recombination, trap density in interfaces, and trap density within the active layer.⁴¹

As shown in Fig. 3a and Fig. S9a (ESI†), a slight decline in electron or hole mobility, even less than one order of magnitude, can result in an obvious decrease in FF but invisible change in J_{SC} . In Fig. 3b, Langevin recombination with a prefactor ranging from 0 to 1 was set as an independent variable to investigate the effect of the bimolecular recombination,⁴² and a gradual decline in V_{OC} and FF was observed with increased recombination. The simulation results align with the findings of the SCLC method and $J_{SC} - P_{light}$ measurements, underlining that the minor changes in hole and/or electron mobility or bimolecular recombination are irrelevant of the reversible degradation. Further simulation introduced electron traps in ZnO and hole traps in MoO_x, both of which led to a pronounced decrease in FF but a minor change in J_{SC} (Fig. S9b-c, ESI†). When electron or hole traps were introduced in the bulk, the simulated parameters degraded evenly, achieving a good fit with the evolution trend of device parameters (Fig. 3c and Fig. S9d, ESI†). However, the recombination model in our experiment described a typical electron capture rate ($1 \times 10^{-8} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$) and a very slow hole capture rate ($1 \times 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$), which led to a reduced Shockley-Read-Hall (SRH) recombination but prolonged electron capture time, resulting in a space charge effect. It is different from typical SRH recombination model^{43,44}, which describes an indirect bimolecular recombination process through a defect with balanced hole and electron capture rate, and can lead to a severe decline in V_{OC} and FF even with a small trap density (Fig. S9e-f, ESI†). Simulation results suggest that the formation of traps under light

stress in the bulk film could cause unbalanced charge carrier capture rates, resulting in observed device degradation.

2.4. Impedance measurements and charge accumulation

Impedance measurements were performed to characterize the distribution of photo-induced trap DOS in devices.⁴⁵ To exclude the improvement influence of the initial TA treatment on interface contact between active layers and charge extraction layers, the dependence of capacitance (C) on voltage (V) and frequency (F) was characterized and compared for both control and devices with pre-TA treatment at 110 °C/10 min before testing. According to the Mott–Schottky equation,

$$C^{-2} = \frac{2}{\varepsilon_0 \varepsilon q N A^2} (V_{bi} - V_{appl})$$

where ε_0 is vacuum permittivity, ε is blend permittivity, q is an elementary charge, N is the trap density, A is the active area, V_{bi} is the built-in voltage and V_{appl} is the external bias. As shown in C – V measurements (Fig. S10a, ESI†), the calculated trap density of fresh, aged and TA-treated devices were 1.54×10^{16} , 1.12×10^{16} , and $7.78 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, respectively. In contrast, for the pre-TA devices (Fig. S10b, ESI†), the calculated trap densities were 7.87×10^{15} , 1.02×10^{16} , and $7.58 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, respectively. In the C – F measurement, the trap DOS distribution was calculated as follows:

$$\text{DOS}(E_\omega) = -\frac{V_{bi}\omega}{qwkt} \frac{dC}{d\omega}$$

$$E_\omega = kT \ln\left(\frac{\omega_0}{\omega}\right)$$

where E_ω is the demarcation energy, k is the Boltzmann constant, w is the depletion width, ω is the modulation frequency and ω_0 is the attempt-to-escape frequency, which is assumed to be 10^{-12} s^{-1} . As shown in Fig. 4, the capacitance of the fresh control devices was higher than that of the pre-TA devices, in constant with the calculated trap density, likely because of an imperfect ZnO or MoO_x interface in

the fresh control devices, which resulted in a wide shallow trap distribution at $E_\omega < 0.4$ eV, and light soaking or TA treatment facilitated the filling of the surface defects in the interface layers. After light ageing process, an increase in capacitance occurred in the low-frequency region of both control and pre-TA devices, corresponding to the trap DOS distribution at $E_\omega = 0.4$ – 0.65 eV. Those traps in both devices decreased after post-TA treatment, and the trap density of 10^{16} cm^{-3} was in accordance with the simulation results. Thus, in stability measurements, the first degradation process was intense because of the combination of irreversible and reversible factors, and the modification of the interface contact of MoO_x resulting in a more effective recovery process than that in subsequent cycles.⁴⁶ The reversible traps at 0.4 – 0.65 eV, distinct from shallow interface defect observed in the first cycle, played a dominant role in the reversible light-induced degradation processes in the multiple cycles.

Fig. 4 (a) $C - F$ dependence and (c) trap DOS distribution verse E_ω for control device. (b) $C - F$ dependence and (d) trap DOS distribution verse E_ω for pre-TA device.

Device photostability can be assessed by monitoring OSCs under the open-circuit mode and short-current mode. In the open-circuit mode, all photogenerated charge carriers recombined within the devices, while in the short-current mode, photogenerated charge carriers could be extracted from the devices and recombined in the external circuit. In the aforementioned measurements, all the devices were set in the open-circuit mode. In Fig. 5a and Fig. S11, ESI†, comparative measurements were conducted by setting the devices in the short-circuit mode, illustrating a minor reversible burn-in amplitude in both J_{SC} and FF compared with the devices under open-circuit mode. These results suggest that the reversible process was closely related to local charge carrier density in devices. Higher concentration of local charge carrier density under the open-circuit mode facilitated the formation of photogenerated traps, and thus resulted in a more pronounced burn-in loss; while relatively smaller concentration of local charge carrier density under short-circuit mode led to a mild burn-in loss. Interestingly, after resetting the test mode for the aged devices from the open-circuit mode to short-circuit mode, it was noted that partial device performance could be restored after approximately 30 h (Fig. 5b).

Driving voltage measurements under constant current are often used in organic light-emitting diodes (OLEDs) to evaluate the stability of radical anions and radical cations. Chemical breaking of high-energy bonds in excited radicals is considered as one of the most crucial pathways for OLED degradation.⁴⁷ In typical driving voltage measurement, a constant current is applied on pure donor materials-based hole-only devices and pure acceptor materials-based electron-only devices, in order to trigger the generation of radical anions or radical cations in the perspective devices and estimate the stability of charged materials under a high-energy excited state upon light exposure. As the material

undergoes degradation, charge carriers are captured by the formation of deep traps, leading to an increase in driving voltage. Herein, pristine material was replaced by a donor:acceptor blend film, which generated opposite minor charge carriers. Residual accumulated carriers in the devices were qualitatively characterized by conducting driving voltage measurements under alternating light and dark environment. Fig. 5c demonstrates that the driving voltage of the PTzBI-dF:Y6-BO-based hole-only device remain stable in the dark condition. Upon light exposure (AM 1.5 G), the driving voltage sharply decreased because a part of majority injected holes was neutralized by photogenerated minority electrons, and the continuous mild decline in driving voltage reflected the competition between charge carrier generation and recombination. Once the light source was removed, the observed dark voltage value was considerably lower than the initial dark voltage, indicating the presence of photogenerated minority electrons accumulated in the device. The number of residual electrons exponentially decayed as a function of time as follows:

$$\delta n(t) = \delta n(0)e^{-t/\tau_{n0}}$$

where $n(0)$ is the initial number of electrons and τ_{n0} is the electron lifetime. Similar findings were obtained for electron-only devices (Fig. 5d). Fig. S12 (ESI†) presents the results of measurements for different donors and acceptors, revealing the existence of long-lived charge accumulation in typical high-performance OPV systems up to minute scale. It is worth noting that and the release process of charge accumulation in different systems varied in magnitude and speed, indicating their dependence on the investigated systems.

Fig. 5 (a) Stability measurements for different external loads under 1 sun illumination, room temperature in nitrogen; yellow dashed lines represent in situ TA treatments at 110 °C for 10 min. (b) Resetting the aged devices under open-circuit mode to short-circuit mode; grey dashed line represents the reset treatment. Driving voltage measurements under constant current 1 mA for (c) hole-only devices and (d) electron-only devices based on PTzBI-dF:Y6-BO systems. Blue area represents measurements in dark, white area represents measurements under AM 1.5G, and grey dashed lines guiding to the initial dark voltage.

3. Discussion

3.1. Light-induced degradation in OSCs

Despite considerable advancements in OPVs, the underlying mechanism of the light-induced degradation in OSCs remains unclear. Previous studies on stability have primarily focused on the fullerene-based systems, attributing device degradation to the factors such as water or oxygen doping, dimerization and over-aggregation of fullerenes. These phenomena result in a loss in light harvesting, the formation of electron traps, and a decrease in charge carrier mobility. Since the emergence of NFAs,

the performance of OSCs was greatly improved in the last few years. However, the fundamental understanding of device degradation still lags behind, particularly in terms of comprehending the different effects of light and heat on the trap formation and their contribution to device degradation.

The generation of traps typically results in increased recombination and hindered extraction, leading to charge accumulation. However, traps that arise from chemical degradation or morphological changes are difficult to reverse through heating, because these traps are considered irreversible and are often accompanied by an increase in energy disorder. Stability measurements under different applied external loads indicate that, charge accumulation might be the cause instead of the outcome of increased trap density and decreased field-dependent charge extraction ability. Similar reversible aging phenomena was reported in P3HT:PCBM systems, which was independent of buffer layers, the thickness of active layer film, and the mixing ratio, but correlated with charge accumulation.⁴⁸ Other following studies have proposed a hypothesis that, the defects were induced by the release of metastable hydrogen from C–H bonds caused by the exposure to high-energy UV light.^{49,50} However, in contrast to these findings of previous studies based on fullerene systems, the results based on NFA systems showed irreversible degradation in V_{OC} . Moreover, the average bond energy of C–C, C–H and C–H bond are 346 kJ/mol, 414 kJ/mol and 485 kJ/mol, respectively, while the maximum energy provided by white LEDs with wavelength of 400–700 nm (< 300 kJ/mol) used for ageing test is below the minimum required energy for chemical breaking, and the in-situ recovery of chemical bonds in blend films is considerably challenging. Therefore, we demonstrate a new hypothesis of physical conversion process rather than chemical breaking in light-induced degradation based on high-performance NFA systems.

3.2. Long-persistent radicals in organic semiconductors

Transformation of charge carriers out of the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) or into the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) can form hole or electron polarons, accompanied by the relaxation of electrons and atoms. These atoms or groups with an unpaired electron are also referred to radicals. In doped OLEDs, acceptor radical anions can dissociate from donor radical cations, diffuse to a region far from the recombination center, and reach a persistent charge separation state, with a fluorescence lifetime up to several hours.^{51,52} The presence of long-persistent radicals in organic conjugated systems is not an isolated phenomenon.^{53,54} In OPV systems, long-persistent radicals were observed in P3HT chloroform solution, which could remain stable for several months.⁵⁵ Researchers once utilized electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) to monitor radicals in OPV polymer donors formed after light ageing or thermal annealing.⁵⁶ Recent studies have also reported that light-induced dihedral twisting in OPV polymer donors can result in the formation of detrimental interchain trapped polaron pairs and increased trap-assist recombination.⁵⁷ However, few studies have systematically investigated the influence of long-persistent radicals on the performance of OSCs, and how do those radicals affect the operational stability. Therefore, combining the aforementioned results, we propose that photogenerated charge carriers can be converted into long-persistent radicals and then accumulated in conjugated blends. As a result, light-induced long-persistent radicals can widely present in undoped OPV systems.

Generally, a conjugated organic molecule receives a charge carrier, forms a polaron, releases the charge carrier quickly, and then returns back to the ground state. However, with prolonged illumination, the blend system remains in a high-energy excited state and contains a high concentration of photogenerated charge carriers. In this situation, the probability of the reorganization process is

significantly increased, allowing the storage of charge carriers in the blend as long-persistent radicals. The formation probability and lifetime of a radical can be evaluated from two aspects. The first aspect is material structure. The ground state of high-performance OPV photoactive materials is non-degenerate, which means that radical anions and cations can reduce system energy through reorganization from an aromatic to quinone structure. Organic semiconductors with degenerate ground states can generate freely movable solitons, while polarons or bipolarons in nondegenerate organic semiconductors have slower mobility and tend to be more stable compared with solitons.⁵⁸ If the photoactive material has uneven low-energy conformation and a large π electron cloud, the lifetime of radicals may be longer. The second aspect is the mixing ratio and morphology of the blend system. Previous studies on OLEDs have proposed that the concentration of long-persistent radicals was associated with the doping ratio.⁵⁹ Thus, a blend system containing low-energy regions, which allows the diffusion of polaron anions or cations far away from the recombination center, may form capacitor-like structures within the device⁶⁰ and facilitate the formation of long-persistent radicals. Thus, we attempt to provide an explanation for the reversible degradation observed in our study: during the light ageing process, illumination induced the formation of long-persistent radicals converted by local charge carriers. As the reaction is reversible, light exposure can also simultaneously provide activation energy and release those radicals, and a suitable TA treatment applied in our experiments can facilitate the releasing process. When the formation and release processes reach an equilibrium, the reversible burn-in loss reached a saturation state.⁵⁰

3.3. DFT calculations and EPR measurements

To evaluate the possibility of radical formation from the perspective of material structures, we

calculated the reorganization energy λ of polymer radical cations by using DFT on B3LYP/6-31G*. In the calculation, a polymer donor was treated as a monomer and a dimer, respectively (Fig. S13 and Table S4, ESI†). The estimated λ value of the dimer cation was 0.0808 eV, which is considerably smaller than that of the monomer cation (0.139 eV), suggesting that the extension of the conjugated main chain can efficiently reduce the reorganization energy barrier of donor cation. EPR measurements further verified the hypothesis of long-persistent radicals. After subjecting blend samples to 20 hours of illumination, weak spin signals were detected, with a signal center g_{eff} of 2.003 (Fig. 6a). Interestingly, it was clearly observed that as the duration of TA treatment at 110 °C increased from 10 to 20 minutes, the spin signal of radicals gradually weakened, and it increased again after the second illumination (Fig. S14a, ESI†). Considering the short duration of illumination on test samples, we determined that the photogenerated radicals did not stem from chemical degradation, but from reversible physical changes. Similar results were also obtained for the PM6:Y6-BO-based system (Fig. S14b, ESI†). Additionally, the spin signals of EPR measurements were found to be dependent on the sample fabrication process (Fig. S14c, ESI†). This suggested that the morphology of the mixed blend exerted a more pronounced impact on the formation of long-persistent radicals than material structure.

Therefore, the mechanism underlying the reversible light degradation can be explained by the presence of long-persistent radicals as illustrated in Fig. 6b and Fig. S15 (ESI†). The difference between HOMO and LUMO energy levels in the polaron state was smaller than that in the ground state because of the relaxation of the electrons and molecular lattice. Under the influence of material structure or blend morphology, polarons tend to generate long-persistent radicals with even lower energy. The long-persistent radicals, as the lowest energetic states of the polaron DOS, functioned as traps within the blend, similar to typical SRH traps with trapped charges, capturing opposite charges

for recombination over a long timescale. Alternatively, these radical-type traps can be released by high-energy light or heat which provide the required activation energy. The presence of long-persistent radicals in the blend hindered charge extraction in the devices, which explains the detrimental impact of ageing process on $FF-P_{\text{light}}$, $J_{\text{ph}}-V_{\text{eff}}$, photo-CELIV and other measurements associated with the extraction process. In addition, because the local charge carrier density can affect the probability of transition from polarons to long-persistent radicals, measurements under the short-circuit mode showed better stability than those under the open-circuit mode. Previous studies on material stability of OLED have pointed out that excited radicals with high-energy chemical bonds are one of the main pathways for chemical degradation. Thus, as it is highly possible that radicals widely exist in OPV systems, it is essential to evaluate the stability of donor radical cations and acceptor radical anions for improving the light stability of OSCs. This can be a reason for the unfavourable long-term stability of reported high-performance OPV systems.

Fig. 6 (a) EPR measurements for PTzBI-dF:Y6-BO blend. (b) Illustration of long-persistent radicals in OSCs.

4. Conclusions

We found that the burn-in loss in high-performance OPV systems can be partially reversed through TA treatment. The reversible J_{SC} and partially reversible FF were accompanied by reversible changes in the field-dependent charge extraction ability, reversible trap DOS distribution at $E_{\omega} = 0.4$ –

0.65 eV as well as minute-scale charge accumulation, and correlated with applied external loads. The irreversible V_{OC} loss correlated with the broadening of the density of states, the enhancement of trap-assist recombination, and the reduced charge carrier lifetime. The electron/hole mobility measured by the SCLC method, bimolecular recombination and active layer morphology measured by GIWAXS exhibited no significant changes before and after light ageing process. Therefore, we proposed a novel degradation mechanism, that light-induced long-persistent radicals are one of the critical factors for burn-in loss during illumination. Under light stress, the presence of high local charge carrier density increases the probability of transition from polarons to long-persistent radicals, whereas a suitable TA treatment can provide sufficient activation energy and facilitate the releasing process in this light-induced reversible process. When formation and release processes reach equilibrium, the reversible burn-in loss becomes saturated. The trapped charges may form a capacitor-like structure within the device, attracting opposite charges and causing space charge effect, and thus hinder charge extraction, similar to typical SRH traps with a trapped charge. As chemical breaking through high-energy excited radicals is one of the main pathways for material degradation, it is crucial to evaluate the stability of excited radicals in OPV systems. Extracting the accumulated charge carriers through reasonable circuit design and usage time planning could be a feasible solution for minimizing the radical effect. More efforts are required for understanding the formation of light-induced radicals from the perspective of molecular structure and morphology. The findings of this study can provide deep insights into light degradation in OSCs and a new perspective for improving the long-term stability of OSCs in terms of material design and device operation.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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